

Iterative Model Matching for 3D Localization of a Mobile Robot

Vinicio Rosas-Cervantes, Soon-Geul Lee

*Department of Mechanical Engineering, Kyung Hee University,
viniciorosas@hotmail.es, sglee@khu.ac.kr*

Abstract

In this study, an algorithm that iteratively matches following models obtained from point clouds is proposed for 3D localization of a mobile robot. Edges derived from point clouds of each scan sampling with a Kinect. After defining a range of interest, the algorithm creates a model by fitting the classified points according to their slope and separation distance. The obtained models are compared with the consecutive closest one of the previous scan in an iterative manner. A transformation matrix is derived from this comparison that calculates displacement and change of orientation of the robot.

Keywords: Mobile robot, localization, Kinect sensor, feature recognition, 3D mapping.

1. Introduction

Localization in a 3D environment requires large point clouds, where the ICP algorithm only works for visual odometry map due to time demanding for real-time implementations. Using the information from both, Inertia Measurement Sensor (IMU) and the encoder, allows the robot to obtain his positioning. However, the response during a long trajectory is affected by the accumulative error on the robot odometry. The sensors are vital for performing the robot localization; the 2D Lidar Laser sensor used for application in 2D mapping and localization (SLAM) [1-2]. Extending this concept, the form in 3D scenarios are evident as it shows on [3], obtaining robust localization. Nevertheless, this process requires a high memory consumption, due to this, the results in real time are limited.

The 3D localization demands an accurate point cloud processing, where the primary duty is to obtain the Range of Interest (ROI) and use it as the reference for localization, map building, and obstacle avoidance. In the case of this paper, the edge detection considered as crucial factor for processing the point cloud [4]. The introduction of a commercial depth camera as Microsoft Kinect, concede a costless sensor for point cloud acquisition, and this sensor already has plenty of applications catching point clouds and detecting keypoints for obstacle avoidance [5-7]. As well, in combination with the grayscale image, generates contouring edges [8]. The recent trend in mobile robot localization, consist in

build a Gaussian observation model [9], using this probabilistic model to track and predict all the robot poses; Moreover, for creating this model requires a robust data, which only could be provided by expensive 3D Lidar sensor.

The proposed algorithm was tested just using an affordable device for 3D mapping, as the Kinect Camera. The method consists in analyzing every point cloud acquire by the robot, determine the Range of Interest (ROI) using the primary corner points, and create a model based on those points. To build this model, a combination of the Random Sample Consensus (RANSAC) with the Split and merge algorithm, classifies the points and create the corresponding model. From the set of models built, the algorithm compares each model with the similar consecutive in an iterative loop. As a result of this circle, a transformation matrix is obtained from every comparison, to compute the robot displacement finally.

2. Material and methods

2.1 Point Cloud acquisition in uneven surface

The mobile robot composes by the following elements: a Turtlebot equipped by a Kobuki Robot, a laptop running Ubuntu Linux 14.0, and a Microsoft Kinect camera. The robot connected to a master station via a Wi-Fi router, the master station is working with Matlab, using the Robotics Tool Box 1.4, which allows an interface among the Matlab and Robotics Operating System (ROS) installed in the local laptop connected to the Robot.

The experiment scenario, is one engineering building corridors, sited a ramp to emulate an uneven surface, with an inclination of $\alpha=10^\circ$.

2.2 Model Creation

Once generated the point cloud, the goal of the algorithm, is detect the primary edges on the point cloud, creating a model based on those edges points.

With the edges points located, the following step detects the range of interest (ROI). For this, the edge points, are organized in polar coordinates, to assign every point (r_n, θ_n) an index according with his polar angle.

Figure 1. Scenario Description

Next, the slope is calculated from one point and the consecutive one (r_{n+1}, θ_{n+1}), in combination with the Split and Merge Algorithm (3) where if $D(r_n, r_{n+1}) > D_{thd}$ then, the segments are separated. Next, the each segment is analyze, to determine which has the biggest amount the horizontal and vertical points, using as a reference the slope angle previously calculated, obtaining a classification of all the edge points for the desired ROI.

$$D(r_n, r_{n+1}) = \sqrt{r_n^2 + r_{n+1}^2 - 2r_n r_{n+1} \cos \Delta\theta}. \quad (3)$$

Finally applying line fitting in the ROI, allows the extraction on a vertical and horizontal line, corresponding to main edges in the point cloud acquired by the robot.

Figure 2. Line fitting

2.3 Localization based in Model Matching

Once the corresponding model is extracted from every point cloud, each model is matched with the consecutive one, obtaining a transformation matrix (4) from every matching, that allows to calculate the angles $[\varphi, \beta, \gamma]$ and determine the robot displacement.

3. Experiment and results

The experiment was conducted with the conditions detail in the material and method section, for executing the ICMM algorithm, the robot is working under the mode of Stop and Scan, acquiring a point cloud (PC_n) for every robot position, besides, with the data from Encoder and IMU sensor.

Once is obtained a point cloud from every robot position, the ICMM algorithm applies, having a total simplification on the point cloud, making the computation faster and accurate. With the all the models generated from every robot position allows calculating the transformation matrix from 2 adjacent locations in an iterative manner, obtaining the displacement in x, y, and z-axis to finally combine with the localization data provided by the odometer and IMU. As a result, the robot trajectory and localization.

4. Conclusion and future work

The experiment conducted, shows the applicability of the ICMM algorithm for 3D mobile robot localization on an uneven surface. Generating and matching two following closest models. The algorithm works efficiently in the robot equipped with a basic configuration to perform 3D mapping, showing valid results to perform localization, without an expensive 3D Lidar Sensor. The model extraction could be improved, detecting and matching irregular shapes, and then applying the ICMM algorithm in outdoors scenarios.

Figure 3. Consecutive Model Matching

Figure 3. Robot Trajectory

References

- [1] N. Engelharda, F. Endresa, J. Hess, J. Sturm, and W. Burgard, "Real-time 3D visual SLAM with a hand-held RGB-D camera," in Proceedings of the RGB-D Workshop on 3D Perception in Robotics, Vasteras, Sweden, 2011.
- [2] H. Durrant-Whyte and T. Bailey, "Simultaneous localization and mapping: part I," IEEE Robotics and Automation Magazine, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 99–108, 2006.
- [3] M. Bosse and R. Zlot, "Map matching and data association for largescale 2D laser scan-based SLAM," Int. J. Robot. Res., vol. 27, no. 6, pp. 667–691, Jun. 2008
- [4] Lin, Y.B.; Wang, C.; Cheng, J. Line segment extraction for large scale unorganized point clouds. ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens, pp. 172–183, 2015.
- [5] M. Bosse and R. Zlot, "Continuous 3D scanmatching with a spinning 2D laser", IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation: pp. 4312 – 4319, 2009.
- [6] N. Engelharda, F. Endresa, J. Hess, J. Sturm, and W. Burgard, "Real-time 3D visual SLAM with a hand-held RGB-D camera," in Proceedings of the RGB-D Workshop on 3D Perception in Robotics, Vasteras, Sweden, 2011.
- [7] Borges, P.; Zlot, R.; Bosse, M.; Nuske, S.; Tews, A. Vision-based localization using an edge map extracted from 3D laser range data. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA), Anchorage, AK, USA, pp. 3–7 May 2010.
- [8] C. Weber, S. Hahmann and H. Hagen. "Methods for feature detection in point clouds," Visualization of large and unstructured data sets applications in geospatial planning, modeling and, pp. 90-99, 2011.
- [9] T. Stoyanov, M. Magnusson, H. Andreasson, A.J. Lilienthal, Path planning in 3D environments using the normal distributions transform, in: IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems, IROS, 2010.
- [10] S. Rusinkiewicz and M. Levoy, "Efficient variants of the ICP algorithm," International Conference on 3-D Digital Imaging and Modeling, 2001.
- [11] N. Fioraio and K. Konolige, "Realtime visual and point cloud slam," in Proceedings of the RGB-D Workshop on Advanced Reasoning with Depth Cameras at Robotics: Science and Systems Conference (RSS '11), 2011.
- [12] T. Hervier, S. Bonnabel, F. Goulette, "Accurate 3D Maps from Depth Images and Motion Sensors via Nonlinear Kalman Filtering" 2012 IEEE/RSJ International onference on Intelligent Robots and Systems October 7-12, 2012.
- [13] D. Droschel, J. Stückler, S. Behnke, "Local multi-resolution representation for 6D motion estimation and mapping with a continuously rotating 3D laser scanner", IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation, ICRA, 2014.
- [14] A. Nuechter, K. Lingemann, J. Hertzberg, H. Surmann, "6D SLAM with approximate data association", Int. Conf. on Advanced Robotics, 2005.
- [15] Leonard, J. J., and Feder, H. J. S., A computationally efficient method for large scale concurrent mapping and localization, In Robotics Research-International Symposium, Vol. 9, pp. 169-178 ,(2000).